

Citation Disparities Between COVID-19 and Alzheimer's Research During the 2020 Pandemic Surge

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Topic: Citation Trends in Health Crises

Title: Paste Title of Study (should match the larger title)

Objectives: To compare the citation frequency of biomedical research articles that relate COVID-19 to Alzheimer's disease involving tau protein, focusing on papers published between August and December 2020, in order to assess a lack of scholarly attention to neurodegeneration during the height of the pandemic.

Background: COVID-19 research received an unprecedented surge in citations that had not been observed in any prior field. However, citation trends in COVID-19 literature during the pandemic have yet to be systematically compared to those in other longstanding medical domains. For example, bibliometric studies show that Alzheimer's disease research, particularly in areas like tau protein, has steadily trended toward higher early citation rates.

Analyzing how a sudden global health emergency alters citation dynamics in established research areas can offer insight into balancing emergent priorities with sustained scientific inquiry.

Methods: Articles were collected from the Web of Science Core Collection using the keywords "COVID," "Alzheimer's disease," "tau protein," and "Coronavirus." Results were reviewed, and non-health-related articles were excluded manually. The final sample included 100 articles published between August and December 2020 consisting of 46 COVID-19 related articles and of 54 Alzheimer's disease related articles. Citation counts were recorded for each article for comparative analysis.

Results: Citation counts for 100 articles published between August and December 2020 were compared between COVID-19 (n = 46) and Alzheimer's (n = 54) groups. The analysis assigned and summed citation ranks, with the Alzheimer's group having a rank sum of 717. The Wilcoxon rank sum test returned $W = 717$ with a p-value of 0.0018, indicating a statistically significant difference in citation distributions during this period.

Conclusions: COVID-19 articles published between August and December 2020 received significantly more citations than Alzheimer's-focused articles from the same period. This suggests a shift in research attention during the height of the pandemic. While such prioritization may reflect urgent public health needs, it raises concerns about the visibility of other critical health topics. Understanding these citation patterns can help inform how scholarly focus shifts during crises.